

Amahuaca

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Anj Droë, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Religious Group, South American Religions

The Amahuaca are an indigenous South American group living in what is now eastern Peru and Brazil. This entry focuses on ethnographic evidence collected during fieldwork with the Peruvian Amahuaca around 1960, at which time Amahuaca society had been drastically reduced to a fraction of its former population through a combination of external warfare with encroaching rubber prospectors and introduced disease. In 1960, most of the Amahuaca resided with Protestant or Dominican missionaries (Dole, 2020:1). However, many aspects of the traditional religion were maintained. The Amahuaca believed in a variety of non-human spirits that could reside in specific animals or plants. These spirits were generally feared, but could be manipulated and communicated with (Dole, 2020:7). Magic played an important role in ensuring success in hunting or other risky endeavors. For the Amahuaca, religious beliefs were inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life. Therefore, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society at large.

Date Range: 1945 CE - 1970 CE

Region: Upper Inuya River, ca. 1960

Region tags: Peru

Upper Inuya River, Peru, ca. 1960

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, George P. 1962-1971. *Ethnographic Atlas*. Ethnology 1-10.
- Source 3: Murdock, George P., and Suzanne F. Wilson. 1972. "Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-cultural codes 3." *Ethnology* 11, no. 3: 254-295.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=se06-003>
- Source 1 Description: Carneiro, Robert L. (Robert Leonard). 1964a. "The Amahuaca and the Spirit World." *Ethnology* Vol. 3 (no. 1): 6-11.
- Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=se06-002>

- Source 2 Description: Carneiro, Robert L. (Robert Leonard). 1964b. "Shifting Cultivation among the Amahuaca of Eastern Peru." In *Beiträge Zur Völkerkunde Südamerikas; Festgabe Für Herbert Baldus Zum 65. Geburtstag*. [Redaktion: Hans Becher, 9-18. Hannover: Kommissionsverlag Münstermann-Druck.
- Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=se06-004>
- Source 3 Description: Carneiro, Robert L. (Robert Leonard). 1970. "Hunting and Hunting Magic among the Amahuaca of the Peruvian Montaña." *Ethnology* Vol. 9 (no. 4): 331-41.
- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=se06-000>
- Source 1 Description: Dole, Gertrude Evelyn. 2020. "Culture Summary: Amahuaca." New Haven: Human Relations Area Files.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "These crops are weeded, along with numerous fruits and vegetables that the Amahuaca have adopted from Peruvians and missionaries" (Dole, 2020:2).

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: "As part of recent changes, Amahuaca in the riverine communities, especially those on Chumichinia Island, have borrowed ceramic and basketry design, cloth mosquito nets, strongly alcoholic manioc beer, and some oral lore from the nearby Conibo and Campa" (Dole, 2020:2).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (Resolved Rating), internal warfare among the Amahuaca is rated 4.75, which is between "Internal warfare seems to occur every year, but usually only during a particular season (original code 4)" and "Internal warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year (original code 5)" (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (Resolved Rating), external warfare among the Amahuaca is rated 4.25, which is between "External warfare seems to occur every year, but usually only during a particular season (original code 4)" and "External warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year (original code 5)" (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Membership is consequently assumed to be assigned at birth.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Therefore, it is assumed that the religion has political support.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 500

Notes: "The population of the Amahuaca, estimated at 6,000 to 9,000 around 1900 (von Hassel 1905:31), is today no more than about 500" (Carneiro, 1970:331).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972, Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures), "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972:259, 271; note: equivalent to SCCS Variable 66)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "Spirits of dead relatives are thought to fly to a place in the sky near the sun, where hunting is easy and they can visit with others who have preceded them" (Dole, 2020:8).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Spirits of dead relatives are thought to fly to a place in the sky near the sun, where hunting is easy and they can visit with others who have preceded them" (Dole, 2020:8).

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Spirits of dead relatives are thought to fly to a place in the sky near the sun, where hunting is easy and they can visit with others who have preceded them" (Dole, 2020:8).

Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Notes: "Spirits of dead relatives are thought to fly to a place in the sky near the sun, where hunting is easy and they can visit with others who have preceded them" (Dole, 2020:8).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "The body of a deceased person is buried temporarily in the house floor, and then cremated after relatives arrive from other communities. The ashes are reburied, and charcoal from the funeral pyre is thrown into the river. Fragments of charred bones and teeth are ground, mixed with soup, and consumed by the closest relative" (Dole, 2020:8).

Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: "The body of a deceased person is buried temporarily in the house floor, and then cremated after relatives arrive from other communities" (Dole, 2020:8).

Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "The body of a deceased person is buried temporarily in the house floor, and then cremated after relatives arrive from other communities" (Dole, 2020:8).

Cannibalism:

– Yes

Notes: "Fragments of charred bones and teeth are ground, mixed with soup, and consumed by the closest relative" (Dole, 2020:8).

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment: Original Scale, "secondary contact with the body or bones is the preferred means of disposal for all or nearly all adult members of the society" (Schroeder, 2001; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Yes

Notes: "The body of a deceased person is buried temporarily in the house floor, and then cremated after relatives arrive from other communities. The ashes are reburied, and charcoal from the funeral pyre is thrown into the river" (Dole, 2020:8).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "The body of a deceased person is buried temporarily in the house floor, and then cremated after relatives arrive from other communities" (Dole, 2020:8).

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: "The body of a deceased person is buried temporarily in the house floor, and then cremated after relatives arrive from other communities" (Dole, 2020:8).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of previously human spirits, non-human supernatural beings, and mixed human-divine beings. See questions below for details.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, High Gods, a supreme high god is "Absent or not reported" (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Celestial bodies are spirits of people who once lived on earth" (Dole, 2020:7).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "Celestial bodies are spirits of people who once lived on earth" (Dole, 2020:7).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The only kind of supernatural beings which the Amahuaca consider to exist today and to play an active role in human affairs is a class of spirits known as yoshi. . . . The animals universally accepted as having yoshi are the jaguar, puma, ocelot, porpoise, electric eel, cayman, anaconda, boa constrictor, rattlesnake, carrion eagle, and king vulture" (Carneiro, 1964a:6).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "Ordinarily yoshi are seen only at night" (Carneiro, 1964a:7).

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: ". . . although a person can not see a yoshi during the day, he may inadvertently touch one. If this happens, the person will recoil, frightened, and take sick, since the yoshi will have stolen his soul" (Carneiro, 1964a:7).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: ". . . not all nocturnal encounters with yoshi are harmful; indeed, people often look forward to seeing them. The reason is that, since yoshi wander freely and widely, they learn a great deal about what is going on and can transmit this information to a person who encounters them" (Carneiro, 1964a:7).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: ". . . not all nocturnal encounters with yoshi are harmful; indeed, people often look forward to seeing them. The reason is that, since yoshi wander freely and widely, they learn a great deal about what is going on and can transmit this information to a person who encounters them" (Carneiro, 1964a:7).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: ". . . not all nocturnal encounters with yoshi are harmful; indeed, people often look forward to seeing them. The reason is that, since yoshi wander freely and widely, they learn a great deal about what is going on and can transmit this information to a person who encounters them" (Carneiro, 1964a:7).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: ". . . not all nocturnal encounters with yoshi are harmful; indeed, people often look forward to seeing them. The reason is that, since yoshi wander freely and widely, they learn a great deal about what is going on and can transmit this information to a person who encounters them" (Carneiro, 1964a:7).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: "One Amahuaca on Chumichinia told us that he had seen and learned a great deal about automobiles, machines, and other aspects of city life from yoshi" (Carneiro, 1964a:8).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: "To a certain extent yoshi are thought to have fore-knowledge, and they may warn a person that someone is planning to kill him" (Carneiro, 1964a:7).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Some yoshi, like those of the carrion eagle, ocelot, and shihuahuaco tree, have the power and inclination to work sorcery entirely on their own initiative" (Carneiro, 1964a:9).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: ". . . although a person can not see a yoshi during the day, he may inadvertently touch one. If this happens, the person will recoil, frightened, and take sick, since the yoshi will have stolen his soul" (Carneiro, 1964a:7).

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Notes: "Yoshi do not eat or sleep, and they have no personal names" (Carneiro, 1964a:7).

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Anthropomorphic

Notes: "Although yoshi are the spirits of animals and plants, they are thought of as anthropomorphic" (Carneiro, 1964a:7).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Occasionally, however, after having had intercourse with a xawakáñdiwo [a type of yoshi or non-human supernatural being], a woman may become pregnant. The offspring resulting from such a union is always identifiable because it is born with some physical impairment or deformity. It is called a yoshiwakĩ, spirit child" (Carneiro, 1964a:10).

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "Occasionally, however, after having had intercourse with a xawakáñdiwo [a type of yoshi or non-human supernatural being], a woman may become pregnant. The offspring resulting from such a union is always identifiable because it is born with some physical impairment or deformity. It is called a yoshiwakĩ, spirit child" (Carneiro, 1964a:10).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of supernatural monitoring.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: "The Amahuaca tell of a rather important culture hero, Rantanka, who taught them how to plant, how to hunt, how to make stone axes, and so forth, but he no longer plays a role in their lives, and in fact most informants say he is dead" (Carneiro, 1964a:6).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual

abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: "Immediately preceding and following a seance men are supposed to abstain from sexual relations" (Carneiro, 1964a:9).

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: "Immediately preceding and following a seance men are supposed to abstain from sexual relations" (Carneiro, 1964a:9).

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: "Another characteristic of yoshi [non-human supernatural being]-possessing animals is that they are considered unfit to eat" (Carneiro, 1964a:7).

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– I don't know

Notes: Ethnographic indicates the presence of permanent or painful bodily alterations, but not that they are required: "Strips of inner bark from a tree with a very caustic sap are occasionally tied around a boy's wrists or forearms, burning a ring around the arm which remains as a permanent scar" (Carneiro, 1970:339).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: "The Amahuaca make no offerings or sacrifices to yoshi and direct no prayers toward them" (Carneiro, 1964a:8). Furthermore, no ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: "The Amahuaca make no offerings or sacrifices to yoshi and direct no prayers toward them" (Carneiro, 1964a:8). Furthermore, no ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: "The Amahuaca make no offerings or sacrifices to yoshi and direct no prayers toward them" (Carneiro, 1964a:8). Furthermore, no ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: "The Amahuaca make no offerings or sacrifices to yoshi and direct no prayers toward them" (Carneiro, 1964a:8).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: "The Amahuaca make no offerings or sacrifices to yoshi and direct no prayers toward them" (Carneiro, 1964a:8).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of rituals intended to ensure the success of individual hunters. See Carneiro, 1970:338-340 for more information.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of a community-wide harvest festival with multiple religious elements. See Dole, 2020:7 for more information.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of extra-ritual in-group markers, including scarification and food taboos. See questions below for details.

Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: "Strips of inner bark from a tree with a very caustic sap are occasionally tied around a boy's wrists or forearms, burning a ring around the arm which remains as a permanent scar" (Carneiro, 1970:339).

Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: "Another characteristic of yoshi [non-human supernatural being]-possessing animals is that they are considered unfit to eat" (Carneiro, 1964a:7).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: The Amahuaca do not have jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 10: Descent) indicate that the Amahuaca have bilateral descent without kindreds. Additionally, the Amahuaca live in exogamous communities without localized clans or lineal kin groups (Murdock, 1962-1971, columns 19, 20, 22). Information on jurisdictional hierarchy and kin ties indicates that the Amahuaca are most accurately characterized as a band.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– I don't know

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of formal education. However, it is unclear whether formal education is provided by the Amahuaca or another society: "Children, especially boys, attend school for a few years and bilingualism is common" (Dole, 2020:2).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of formal education. However, it is unclear whether formal education is provided by the Amahuaca or another society: "Children, especially boys, attend school for a few years and bilingualism is common" (Dole, 2020:2).

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: During the time focus of this entry, the Amahuaca did not have jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a band society (SCCS Variable 237, Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond Local Community; retrieved from Divale, 2004). See question above regarding levels of social complexity.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 90, Police, police functions among the Amahuaca are not specialized (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 149, Scale 1 [of Cultural Complexity] - Writing and Records, the Amahuaca do not possess a distinct written language (Murdock and Provost, 1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: "The onset of the dry season marks the beginning of the new year for the Amahuaca" (Carneiro, 1964b:10).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society itself, this entry assumes that the religious group provides food for itself. The Amahuaca depend primarily on small-scale agriculture (SCCS Variables 207, Dependence on Agriculture, and 232, Intensity of Cultivation), with hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) as a secondary means of subsistence. Fishing (SCCS Variable

205, Dependence on Fishing) supplements the diet (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas columns 7 and 28).

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Amahuaca depend primarily on small-scale agriculture (SCCS Variables 207, Dependence on Agriculture, and 232, Intensity of Cultivation), with hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) as a secondary means of subsistence. Fishing (SCCS Variable 205, Dependence on Fishing) supplements the diet (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas columns 7 and 28).